

EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTS OF RATES AND TIMES OF RICEBRAN APPLICATION ON THE PERFORMANCE OF SOYABEANS (*Glycine max L. Merril*) AND SORGHUM (*Sorghum bicolor L. Moench*) INTERCROP IN THE GUINEA SAVANNA OF NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

A field experiment was carried out in Badeggi (Guinea Savanna) of Nigeria, to determine the effects of rates and times of ricebran (Rb) application on soyabean and sorghum intercrop growth parameters, yield components and yields. Four Rb application rates of 0, 2, 4 and 6 t/ha and five Rb application times of 0, 14, 28, 42 and 56 Days Before Planting (DBP) were evaluated. The experiment was a 4 x 5 factorial in a randomized complete block design. There were twenty treatments replicated three times. Result obtained indicated that at the time the component crops were planted, immobilization of nutrients from the Rb by soil microorganism was still taking place in the treatments Rb applied at 0, 14 and 28 DBP. On the other hand, mineralization of nutrients from the body of the soil microorganism had commenced at planting time in the treatments Rb applied at 42 and 56 DBP. The treatment Rb applied at the rate of 2 t/ha and at 42 DBP was best synchronized with the component crops plant nutrient requirement. This treatment also resulted in significantly higher ($P \leq 0.05$) yields of the component crops than the others.

KEYWORDS: Ricebran, Application Rates, Times, Sorghum, Soyabean.

INTRODUCTION

Soils in the savanna are often deficient in Nitrogen (N) Phosphorus (P), Potassium (K) Organic matter (OM) and Cat-ion Exchange Capacity (CEC). Furthermore, the clay in these areas is Kaolinite, which is low activity clay (Sanchez and Jama, 2002). NISER (2003) reported that Nigerian farmers have limited access to inorganic fertilizer because of low production, procurement and distribution. Furthermore, the use of inorganic fertilizer alone have been reported to have negative effects on the environment, such as nitrate leaching, ground water pollution, degradation of soil structure, decrease in soil pH and surface water infiltration (Pounded *et al.*, 2001). The use of organic material to enhance soil fertility was a popular practice among the peasant farmers, before the advent of mineral fertilizer. Many farmers are now reverting to this old practice. In Badeggi, and many other rice producing areas of the Guinea savanna, ricebran (Rb) an organic bi-product of rice processing is available in abundance. Farmers get Rb burnt before incorporating it into the soil, as a source of nutrients, but N, S and C contents of the Rb, are lost in the process. In addition, burning leads to the production of the green house gas carbon dioxide (CO₂), which has been implicated as one of the major causes of global warming. Information on the use of Rb as a source of nutrient and organic matter is presently lacking. Thus, the need to develop a more sustainable technology that will reduce the amount of nitrogen, sulphur and carbon lost, when Rb is used as a source of nutrients and organic matter, in crop production.

The objective of this experiment was to determine the Rb application rate and time required for optimum yields of soyabean and sorghum intercrop.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A field experiment was conducted in Badeggi (Guinea savanna agro-ecological zone) Nigeria in 2005 and 2006. The experimental area (34 x 27.5 m) was ploughed, harrowed and ridged. The gross plot size (4 x 3 m) consisted of four ridges spaced 0.75 m apart, while the net plot size (3 x 1.5 m) was obtained from the two central ridges of each plot. The soyabean variety TGX 1448-2E was drilled on the crest of each ridge, at a between and within the ridge plant spacing of 0.75 and 0.05 m respectively, to give a plant population of 266,666 plants/ha. Sorghum seedlings, red seeded farmer's variety were intercropped on the lower side of the ridge, on the same day soyabean was planted. Sorghum plant spacing was 0.75 m between the ridge and 1.0 m within the ridge to give a plant population of 13,333 plants/ha. There were twenty treatments which was made up of Rb application rates of 0, 2, 4, and 6 t/ha and application times of 0, 14, 28, 42 and 56 Days Before Planting (DBP). The experiment was a 5 x 4 factorial in a

randomized complete block design with three replicates. Pre-planting composite soil samples were obtained at random with a soil auger at 0-15 cm depth from the experimental site. Soil samples were also obtained in a similar manner at planting time. This was to determine if immobilization of N by soil microorganisms was still in progress or if mineralization had commenced in any of the Rb treatments. Each soil sample was put into a plastic bucket and properly mixed. Soil aggregates were crushed with the use of a pestle and mortar. The crushed soil sample was dried at room temperature and sieved through a 2 mm sieve before it was taken to the laboratory for analyses. The samples were analyzed for chemical and physical properties. Soil total – N were determined using the kjeldal method (Bremnar, 1965), soil pH was determined in a 1:2 w/v soil liquid suspension. Soil texture was determined using the hydrometer method (Gee and Baurnder, 1986). Available phosphorus was determined using the Bray P₋₁ method (Bray and Kurtz, 1945). Potassium (K), Ca and Mg were first extracted using neutral normal NH₄.0AC, there after K was determined using flame emission in the Perkin – Elmer 5000 spectrometer, while Mg and Ca were determined using atomic absorption spectrophotometer and ECEC was computed as the sum of exchangeable bases plus exchangeable acidity. Soyabean and sorghum growth parameters, yield component and yields were obtained and subjected to statistical analysis using ANOVA. Significant means were separated by the Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Soil test

Result of the analyzed soil samples indicated that in treatments where ricebran (Rb), were applied at 0, 14 and 28 Days Before Planting (DBP), the soil pH remained acidic with the value ranging from 4.9 to 5.4. The total N, available P and effective cat-ion exchange capacity (ECEC) were below their critical levels (Tables 2 and 3). This is an indication that immobilization of nutrients from the Rb by soil microorganism was still in progress at the time of planting in these treatments. Treatments planted, when immobilization of nutrients from the Rb was still in progress at the time of planting, showed low nutrient availability and yields of the component crops. This was because some of the nutrients (especially N) that would have been available to the component crops for their growth were utilized by soil microorganism for their own sustenance. In treatments where Rb was applied at 42 DBP, the soil pH, total N, available P and ECEC, increased from an average, of 5.0, 0.04 g/kg, 2.65 mg/kg and 1.58 cmol kg⁻¹ respectively when Rb was not applied, (Table 1) to 6.5, 0.44 g/kg, 12 .4 mg/kg and 4.16 cmol kg⁻¹ respectively when Rb was applied at 42 DBP and at the rate of 2 t/ha. This is an indication that mineralization of nutrients, from the body of the soil microorganism had commenced, at the time of planting in this treatment. Treatments that were planted at 42 DBP when mineralization of nutrient had commenced, showed high nutrient availability and yield of the component crops. The reduced availability of nutrients in the treatment Rb applied at 56 DBP was probably due to the fact that mineralization of nutrients had commenced much earlier at about 42 DBP. Thus at 56 DBP, a lot of the nutrients like the N and cat-ions had been lost.

Soyabean growth parameters, yield components and yields

Soyabean plant height were significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) enhanced by the application of ricebran (Rb) in 2005, especially when the Rb was applied at 42 DBP and at the rates of 2, 4 and 6 t/ha (Table 4). In 2006, there were no significant differences in soyabean plant height, at the different Rb application treatments.

The highest number of soyabean pods per plant (i.e. 28) was obtained when Rb was applied at the rate of 2 t/ha and at 42 DBP in 2005 and 2006. This number of pods per plant was however, not significantly different from those obtained, at the other Rb application treatments.

Rb applied at the rate of 2 t/ha and at 42 DBP produced the highest soyabean stover yields of 1900 and 3, 111.1 kg/ha in 2005 and 2006 respectively. These stover yields were significantly higher ($P \leq 0.05$) than those obtained at the other Rb application treatments in both years.

Rb applied at 42 DBP and at the rates of 2, 4 and 6 t/ha enhanced soyabean grain yields significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) in 2005. In 2006 there were no significantly differences in soyabean yields at the different Rb application treatments. All the same, Rb applied at the rate of 2 t/ha and at 42 DBP produced the highest soyabean yield of 1072. Kg/ha in this year. The interaction effects of Rb application rates and times on soyabean grain yield, were not significantly different in 2005 but significantly different ($P \leq 0.01$) in 2006 (Table 6).

Sorghum growth parameters yield components and yields

In 2005, Rb applied at 42 and 14 DBP and at the rate of 2 t/ha resulted in sorghum plant heights of 200.5 and 207 cm respectively, which were significantly higher ($P \leq 0.05$) than the plant heights obtained at the other Rb application rates and times (Table 5). In 2006, there were no significant differences in sorghum plant heights at the different Rb application rates and times.

The application of Rb at the rates of 2, 4 and 6 t/ha and at 42 DBP significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) enhanced sorghum stover yields in 2005. In 2006, Rb application rates of 2, 4 and 6 t/ha also significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) enhanced sorghum stover yields. However, there were no significant differences between the times of Rb application.

Rb applied at the rate of 2 t/ha and at 42 DBP, produced the highest sorghum grain yield of 1076.5 kg/ha in 2005. This yield was significantly higher ($P \leq 0.01$) than the yields obtained at the other Rb treatments. Similar trends were obtained in 2006 with the exception that Rb application times were not significantly different. The interaction effects of Rb application rates and times on sorghum grain yields, were significantly ($P \leq 0.01$) different in 2005 and 2006 (Table 7).

CONCLUSION

The treatment Rb applied at the rate of 2 t/ha and at 42 DBP was better synchronized with the component crops plant nutrient requirements than other Rb application treatments. This treatment also produced significantly higher ($P \leq 0.05$) sorghum and soyabean growth parameters, yield components and yields than the other Rb treatments. (Yusuf *et al.*, 2006).

Table 1: Soil test result of the composite soil sample obtained before planting and rice bran application.

<i>Soil properties</i>	<i>2005</i>	<i>2006</i>	<i>Average</i>
pH (H ₂ O)	5.10	4.90	5.00
Organic carbon (g/kg)	0.77	0.78	0.78
Total N (g/kg)	0.04	0.04	0.04
Available P (mg/kg)	2.80	2.50	2.65
Exchangeable cat-ions			
Ca (cmol kg ⁻¹)	0.24	0.22	0.23
Mg “	1.24	1.19	1.22
K “	0.07	0.07	0.07
Na “	0.03	0.04	0.04
Total			
Acidity “	0.03	0.03	0.03
ECEC “	1.61	1.55	1.58
Sand g/kg	895.50	889.60	892.55
Silt “	83.40	83.50	83.45
Clay “	21.10	26.90	24.00
Textural class	sandy	sandy	sandy

Table 2: Effects of rates (0,2,4,6 t/ha) and times (0,14,28,42,56 DBP) of ricebran application on soil chemical properties at planting of sorghum and soyabean intercrop.

Soil Properties	2005														
	-----0-----				-----14-----				-----28-----						
	-----42-----		-----56-----		0	2	4	6	0	2	4	6	0	2	4
pH (H ₂ O)	5.0	5.1	6.5	6.2	5.0	5.2	5.1	5.0	5.0	5.2	5.2	5.1	4.9	5.4	5.1
O.C (g/kg)	1.3	0.8	0.8	0.8	1.2	0.7	0.7	0.8	1.1	1.2	1.4	0.7	0.9	0.8	
T.N (g/Kg)	0.03	0.03	0.44	0.42	0.40	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.05	0.03	0.02	
Av.P(mg/kg)	2.8	2.2	12.4	10.7	10.23	3.3	4.6	6.2	7.2	2.6	2.5	2.9	2.6	2.7	
Ca (cmolkg ⁻¹)	0.2	0.2	1.8	1.4	1.2	0.2	0.8	0.9	0.9	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	
Mg	1.2	0.4	1.9	1.6	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.2	1.2	1.4	1.3	1.2	0.7	1.4	1.2
K	0.08	0.1	0.4	0.6	0.6	0.07	0.07	0.09	0.08	0.08	0.05	0.09	0.08	0.05	0.05
Na	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.02	
Total Acidity	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.03
ECEC	1.54	0.76	4.16	3.66	3.16	0.73	1.86	2.06	2.05	1.70	1.56	1.10	1.72	1.50	

Table 3: Effects of rates (0,2,4,6 t/ha) and times (0,14,28,42,56 DBP) of ricebran application on soil chemical properties at planting of sorghum /soyabean intercrop.

Soil Properties	2006															
	-----0-----				-----14-----				-----28-----							
	-----42-----		-----56-----		0	2	4	6	0	2	4	6	0	2	4	6
0	2	4	6	0	2	4	6	0	2	4	6	0	2	4	6	
pH (H ₂ O)				4.9	5.2	5.0	5.1	4.9	5.0	5.1	5.2	4.8		5.3	5.1	
	5.0	5.0	6.3	6.1	6.0	5.0	5.2	5.4	5.4							
O.C (g/kg)				0.7	1.3	1.8	1.9	0.7	0.8	1.1	1.2	0.7	0.8	0.9	1.2	
	0.7	0.8	0.9	1.3	0.7	0.8	-	-								
T.N (g/Kg)				0.03	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.04	0.03		0.03	
	0.03	0.03	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.03	0.04	0.9	1.2							
Av.P (mg/kg)				2.9	2.9	2.9	2.8	2.6	2.5	2.8	2.8	3.0	2.6		2.6	
	3.2	2.1	11.8	10.3	9.9	2.9	3.9	6.9	6.7							
Ca (cmolkg ⁻¹)				0.2	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	
	0.2	1.7	1.5	1.4	0.2	0.8	0.8	0.9								
Mg	“			1.1	1.2	1.0	1.1	1.1	1.1	1.2	1.2	0.7	1.4	1.1	1.0	
	0.1	1.8	1.4	1.2	0.6	0.8	0.9	1.0								
K	“			0.09	0.07	0.08	0.09	0.09	0.1	0.09	0.1	0.05	0.09		0.05	
	0.06	0.08	0.4	0.6	0.7	0.7	0.07	0.07	0.09							
Na	“			0.03	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	
	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03								
Total																
Acidity “				0.03	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.03	
	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03								
ECEC “				1.45	1.53	1.34	1.57	1.45	1.46	1.65	1.67	1.01	1.75		1.4	
	1.32	0.44	3.96	3.56	3.36	0.93	1.7	1.83	2.05							

Table 5: Effects of rates (0,2,4,6 t/ha) and times (0,14,28,42,56 DBP) of ricebran application on sorghum growth parameters yield components and yields.

-----SORGHUM-----						
Ricebran Application		Yields	Plant	Heights Stover	Yields	
Grain	Times		-----cm-----			
Rates	Times					
kg/ha	DBP		-----cm-----			
t/ha	DBP	2005	2006	2005	2006	2006
0	0	141.8ab	174.3	1850.0f	1777.8ef	
	183.5Lm	444.4bcd				
0	14	102.4b	164.1	1600.0f	2622.2bcdef	
	186.0LM	655.5abcd				
0	28	104.1b	144.1	2150.0ef	833.0f	
	176.0m	208.3d				
0	42	106.5b	174.0	2150.0ef	1888.9ef	
	173.0m	472.2bcd				
0	56	101.9b	174.1	2450.0ef	3222.2abcde	
	199.5L	805.6abcd				
2	0	101.6b	153	2100.0ef	1388.9ef	
	390.0i	347.2cd				
2	14	207.1a	169.9	5500.0abcd	2055.6ef	
	473.5h	513.9abcd				
2	28	166.8ab	159.8	4100.0cde	1555.6ef	
	923.5b	129.6d				
2	42	200.5a	214.9	7150.0a	4500.0abc	
	1076.5a	1124.9abc				
2	56	127.1ab	757.5	3500.0def	2,277.8cdef	
	733..5d	569.1abcd				
4	0	159.9ab	174.6	2500.0ef	3555.6abcde	
	850.0c	888.9abcd				
4	14	132.4ab	174.6	4500.0bcd	2277.8cdef	
	690.0e	569.3abcd				
4	28	165.6ab	175.6	5000.0bcd	3666.7abcde	
	383.5i	937.5abcd				
4	42	192.5ab	160.5	6350.0ab	2777.0bcdef	
	650.0f	694.4abcd				
4	56	165.8ab	115.0	44100.0cde	833.0f	
	166.5m	208.3d				
6	0	174.7ab	228.5	4800.0bc	5444.4a	
	526.5g	1361.1a				
6	14	172.0ab	193.2	5000.0bcd	4333.0abcd	
	340.0j	1083.3abc				
6	28	175.1ab	178.8	5000.0bcd	4888.9ab	
	336.0j	1229.2ab				
6	42	122.1ab	173.0	6000.0abc	2555.6cdef	
	136.5n	861.1abcd				
6	56	143.2ab	183.2	3650.0def	3611.1abcde	
	290.0k	902.8abcd				

N.S

Means with the same letter (S) within the same column are not significantly different ($P \leq 0.05$) according to Duncan's Multiple Range test.

Table 6: Analysis of variance for the effects of rates and times of ricebran application on soyabean yield (Kg/ha).

SOV	DF	SS	2005			
			MS	Computed F	Tabular F 5%	1%
Replicates	2	951957.70	475978.80	3.49	3.25	5.21
Treatments	19	5634705.60	296563.50	2.17*	1.85	2.40
Rate (A)	3	564215.50	188071.80	1.30 ^{N.S}	2.85	4.34
Time (B)	4	1859293.50	464823.40	3.41*	2.62	3.86
A X B	12	3211196.60	267599.70	1.96 ^{N.S}	2.02	2.69
Error	38	5183581.30	136410			
Total	59	11770244.60				

SOV	DF	SS	2006			
			MS	Computed F	Tabular F 5%	1%
Replicates	2	1079852.30	539926.10	1.99 ^{N.S}	3.25	5.21
Treatments	19	1816885.60	95625.60	0.35 ^{N.S}	1.85	2.40
Rate (A)	3	284152.10	94717.40	0.35 ^{N.S}	2.85	4.34
Time (B)	4	831840.30	207960.10	0.77 ^{N.S}	2.62	3.86
A X B	12	12104237.10	1008686.40	3.71**	2.02	2.69
Error	38	10323491.60	271670.80			
Total	59	13220229.50	224071.70			

Table 7: Analysis of variance for the effects of rates and times of ricebran application on sorghum yields (kg/ha).

SOV	DF	SS	2005			
			MS	Computed F	Tabular F 5%	1%
Replicates	2	23.60	11.79	0.079	3.25	5.21
Treatments	19	186466.90	9814	66.04**	1.85	2.40
Rate (A) 3		101182.980	33727.70	226.96**	2.85	4.34
Time (B)	4	7690.70	1922.70	12.94**	2.62	3.86
A X B	12	77593.20	6466.10	43.51**	2.02	2.69
Error	38	5647.340	148.60			
Total	59					

SOV	DF	SS	2006			
			MS	Computed F	Tabular F 5%	1%
Replicates	2	457493.20	228746.60	1.20	3.25	5.21
Treatments	19	6852550.90	360660.60	1.9*0	1.85	2.40
Rate (A)	3	3020222.60	1006740.90	5.4*0	2.85	4.34
Time (B)	4	120911.580	30227.90	0.163 ^{NS}	2.62	3.86
A X B	12	11224389.70	935365.80	5.03**	2.02	2.69
Error	38	7055479.90	185670.50			
Total	59					

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REFERENCES

Bray, R.H. and L.T. Kurtz (1945). Determination of total organic and available form of Phosphorus in soil. Soil Science 59:39-45

Bremnar, J.M. (1965). In organic forms of nitrogen. In: C.A. Black et al (Ed) Method of Soil Analyses. Part 2. Agron mongr. 9 America Society of Agronomy, Madison, WI pp 117-123

Gee, G. W. and J.W. Baunder (1986). Particle size analysis In: A. Khote (Ed) Method of Soil Analysis. Part i. 2nd ed. P 385 411 Agron. Mongr 19ASA and ASSA, Madison W.I.

Nigerian Institute of Social and Economic Research (NISER) (2003): Understanding poverty in Nigeria. College press and publishers Ltd. Ibadan Nigeria. 44IP

Pounded, D.D, Horwarth, W.R., Metchell, J.P, Temple, S.R. (2001). Impact of cropping system on soil nitrogen storage and loss. Agricultural system 68 No-3 91-96.

Sanchez, R.A. and B.A. Jama (2002). Soil fertility replenishment takes off in east and south Africa. In: Integrated Plant Nutrient Management in sub-Sahara Africa: From Concept to Practice, ed. B. Vanlauwe, J. Diels N. Sanginga and R. Merckx. CABI Publishing, Wallingford, U.K 23-45.

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